

Augmented presence detection in buildings

Olivier Steiger, Reto Marek, Reto Häfliger

Hochschule Luzern, Technik & Architektur, 6048 Horw, olivier.steiger@hslu.ch

Abstract

Researchers from Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts have investigated the use of augmented presence detection in buildings. The term refers to the recording of presence (presence yes / no), number, position, activity and identity of persons. Four detection methods have been investigated: (1) Interconnection of conventional room sensors; (2) Proprietary multi-sensor platform; (3) Video-based presence detection; (4) Presence detection using thermal imaging. Measurement accuracies of ± 2 persons were achieved with video-based presence detection using the commercial sensor HPD2 from Steinel. Furthermore, the benefits of augmented presence detection were determined. The use of augmented presence detection enables efficiency increases, more comfort and new applications in buildings. In particular, a significant energy-saving potential has been identified in functional buildings. Based on the investigations, recommendations have been derived for the further development of presence detectors and the use of augmented presence detection in buildings. These are aimed at manufacturers, specialist planners and contractors.

1. Introduction and scope

In Switzerland, 45% of total end energy consumption can be traced back to heating, cooling, ventilation, hot water preparation and lighting of buildings [1]. However, part of this energy is not required because rooms are sometimes left unoccupied. Consequently, the supply of heat / cooling / fresh air / light does not match the actual demand. One way of reducing energy consumption is the occupancy-based control of building services installations. With this, the systems are controlled according to the actual or predicted occupancy of the building.

In order to determine occupancy, various presence detection technologies are available. Passive infrared sensors (PIR) are the most commonly used. These detect people through their heat radiation and are widespread, inexpensive as well as easy to install. However, PIR sensors cannot reliably distinguish persons from other heat sources such as animals, solar radiation, electronic devices. There must also be visual contact between the sensor and the person. Some of these disadvantages can be avoided by using ultrasonic or high frequency radio waves (HF) for presence detection. Ultrasound waves fill out the room completely and detect movements even if there is no visual contact. High-frequency radio waves are able to propagate through glass, wood and lightweight walls. This makes HF sensors suitable for hidden mounting in sanitary installations and public spaces. A more recent type of sensor technology is optical presence detection. With this, the room is monitored by an optical system, usually a video camera. People present in the room are recognized using image processing. In this way, people can not only be detected but also counted, localized and recognized.

In order to determine the actual demand (for energy, comfort, security) more accurately, additional information can be obtained. For example, the number, position, activity and identity of people present in a room can be determined. This goes beyond conventional presence detection (i.e. human presence yes or no) and is therefore referred to as *augmented* presence detection (Figure 1). The detection of augmented presence opens up many new possibilities.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, four different methods for the detection of augmented presence are introduced. In Section 3, the benefits of augmented presence detection in building services applications are discussed. In Section 4, recommendations are made for the further development of presence detectors and the use of augmented presence detection in buildings. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper with some perspectives.

Figure 1 Five manifestations of presence detection in buildings.

2. Detection of augmented presence

The automatic detection of augmented presence information in buildings requires appropriate sensing technologies. Due to the wide variety of existing measurement principles, these can be quite diverse. In practice however, certain fundamental requirements must be met in order to ensure that presence detection can be carried out economically and for the intended purpose. Above all, the technology must be accepted by users and must not violate the protection of personality rights. Also for common applications, sensors are required that do not differ significantly from conventional presence detectors in terms of price, appearance, interfaces and

measurement characteristics. In addition, the installation, commissioning and maintenance of the devices must be as simple as possible.

In several experiments, four different detection methods have been used. Two methods rely on optical presence detection, whilst the others are based on conventional (i.e. non-optical) sensors. The main properties of the investigated methods are summarized in Table 1. It should be noted that currently, only video-based presence detection is available as a commercial product for building applications, for instance from the company Steinel.

All experiments have been conducted under realistic conditions in two meeting rooms and one open space office at Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts [2]. For all practical purposes, the interconnection of conventional room sensors has proven to be useless because the results were very inaccurate and hardly reproducible. Here, more advanced evaluation methods than those used are required, e.g. based on machine learning. With the proprietary multi-sensor platform, the measurement accuracy is about ± 2 persons. However, natural changes in room conditions (e.g. temperature, humidity, air quality) can lead to considerable deviations. Therefore, the variance of the results is generally larger than with optical detection methods. With video-based presence detection (used sensor: Steinel HPD2), the measuring accuracy is about ± 2 persons as well. Various influencing factors have to be taken into account when recording the data: Sensor position, lighting conditions, influence of clothing. Also, the devices should always be used with the latest firmware release due to rapid improvements in image processing. Finally, with presence detection using thermal imaging, sitting persons have been correctly identified in about 90% of all cases. However, non-human heat sources (laptops, coffee cups) have been incorrectly detected as well. Here, appropriate training images have proven to be particularly important for accuracy. Note that detailed experimental results are to be found in the final project report [2].

	Interconnection of conventional room sensors	Proprietary multi-sensor-platform	Video-based presence detection	Presence detection using thermal imaging
Description	Different, conventional room sensors (e.g. temperature, CO ₂ , door/window contact, PIR) are evaluated commonly	Different sensors are combined on a single measurement platform and evaluated commonly	Room occupation is determined using video (visible light) and image processing	Room occupation is determined using video (infrared light) and image processing
Measured values	Presence yes/no, number, (position), (activity)	Presence yes/no, number, (position), (activity), (ID)	Presence yes/no, number, position, activity, ID	Presence yes/no, number, position, (activity), (ID)
Commercial products available for building applications	No	No	Yes	No
Relies on commercially available sensors	Yes	No	No	No
Protection of personality rights	Guaranteed	Depending on used sensors	Sensitive	Sensitive

Table 1 Properties of different augmented presence detection methods [2].

3. Benefits of augmented presence detection

Augmented presence detection provides valuable information about the use of buildings and rooms. This information can in turn be used to improve energy efficiency, comfort, security, functionality and profitability. In order to quantify the corresponding benefits, an extensive literature study has been conducted [2].

Energy efficiency can be improved, for example, by supplementing common, air quality-based ventilation control systems with the occupancy rate of the room [3-5]. Furthermore, in open-plan offices, the personalized conditioning of individual room sections makes sense, if feasible [6-7]. Another decisive factor is the optimal utilization of room capacities. I.e. whenever possible, rooms should be occupied to their full capacity [5, 8]. To this end, current and expected room occupancy must be determined. Note that in residential buildings, augmented presence detection does not make much sense, because it does not cause significant energetic savings and offers few advantages in terms of comfort, safety, functionality and economy. Conversely, conventional presence detection in residential buildings is very useful from an energy point of view. With respect to conventional time-switching programs, significant savings can be achieved.

Comfort can be improved by adapting comfort set points locally to the individual preferences of the users: illuminance, color temperature, glare protection, room climate. Individual preferences are thereby determined based on the activity or ID of present persons. Various options are available for improving safety. For example, the position of persons can be used to detect intruders in predefined areas. During an evacuation, people flow (i.e. number and position over time) and obstacles (congestions) can be dynamically taken into account to automatically determine optimal escape routes. Applications that are not feasible with conventional presence information are also conceivable. For example the visualization of room occupancy in real time for hot-desking or as a basis for planning. Finally, economic profitability can be improved through the optimized use of given resources: rooms, cleaning staff, etc. The necessary data is provided by augmented presence detection. An extensive overview of possible applications of augmented presence detection in buildings is provided in Table 2.

		Presence yes/no	Number	Position	Activity	Identity
ENERGY						
Presence-based control	The building's technical systems are controlled according to the presence of person(s). For example, lighting on / off.	X				
Occupancy-based control	The building's technical systems are controlled according to the number of present persons. For example, volume flow rate, supply air temperature.		X			
Position-based control	The building's technical systems are controlled according to the position of present persons. For example, illuminance, incidence of daylight.			X		
Activity-based control	The building's technical systems are controlled according to the activity of present persons. For example, illuminance, ambient temperature, air quality.				X	
Identity-based control	The building's technical systems are controlled according to the identity of present persons. For example, illuminance, incidence of daylight, ambient temperature, air quality.					X
Demand-based set points	The set points of the building's technical systems are set according to the actual demand. For example, set point for illuminance, ambient temperature, volume flow rate. The demand is determined based on the occupancy, position, activity, group and/or ID of persons as well as other information from the building automation & control system.	X	(X)	(X)	(X)	(X)
Reduction of runtime	The runtimes of the building's technical systems are reduced to the necessary minimum. The required runtimes are determined based on the (predicted) presence in the rooms / room segments.	X		(X)		
Standby in case of non-occupancy	The building's technical systems are set to an energy-saving operating mode when individual rooms / segments are not occupied, e.g. stand-by or economy.	X		(X)	(X)	
Pre-conditioning	Rooms / segments are pre-conditioned according to the predicted occupancy. This creates appropriate room comfort conditions prior to the actual usage of the room.	X		(X)		
COMFORT						
Personalized building automation	Comfort conditions are locally adapted to the preferences of individual users: illuminance, color temperature, glare protection, climate settings. Preferences are determined based on the activity or ID of the person.			X	(X)	(X)

Participatory room conditions setting	Comfort conditions in a given space are determined by consensus. This means that the comfort settings incorporate the preferences of <i>all</i> users that are present in the room. The present users are determined based on their ID.				(X)		X
Pre-conditioning	See above.	X			(X)		
Demand-based transports	Passenger lifts and similar transport systems for buildings are controlled according to current demand. This means that the number and position of waiting as well as transported persons are taken into account to schedule upcoming trips.		X	X			
SAFETY							
Access control	Access to individual rooms / segments is only granted to authorized personnel. Authorizations are determined based on identity.				(X)		X
Intrusion detection	Intruders are signaled by undue presence in supposedly empty rooms. This application takes advantage of the fact that some augmented presence detection methods can distinguish persons from other objects.	X			(X)		
Smart evac	Instead of evacuating buildings according to rigid procedures and fixed routes, people flow and congestions (e.g. due to fires) are dynamically taken into account in order to determine optimal escape. To this end, the number and position of persons must be determined.		X	X			X
Active Assisted Living	Active Assisted Living refers to the assistance of elderly people by technical means. E.g., automatic tumble detection, detection of unusual behavior. This requires the determination of the position, activity and possibly identity of persons.				X	X	(X)
Recognition of left-behinds	Some technical premises (e.g. substations, maintenance shafts) are rarely occupied and carry an increased risk of accidents. Persons left behind in such environments must be detected and evacuated quickly and reliably.	X			(X)	(X)	
FUNCTIONALITY							
Occupancy visualization	The occupancy of rooms (presence, crowd density, position, activity, ID) can be displayed for various purposes. For example, visualization of the occupancy of meeting rooms and workstations, customer density in supermarkets, hotel rooms occupancy.	(X)	(X)	(X)	(X)	(X)	(X)
Basis for planning	Data about the occupancy and usage of existing buildings can be used to tailor the planning of future, similar buildings to their expected usage. For instance, usage profiles (frequency, type of usage) can be taken into account to scale and lay out rooms.		(X)	(X)	(X)		
PROFITABILITY							
Hot desking	Under hot desking, different users share common resources (e.g. workstations) at different times. The respective resources are assigned upon arrival of the user. This saves costs in comparison to permanently assigned resources. The allocation of resources is based on their current occupancy and on the preferences of individual users.		X	X			(X)
Results-oriented facility management	Instead of a rigid cleaning process, results-oriented facility management takes into account the usage of the rooms and the resulting, actual contamination. I.e., only what has been used gets cleaned. The usage of the rooms is determined based on the number, position and activity of present persons.		X	X	(X)		
Reduction of equipment wear and tear	The reduction of running times, demand-driven set points and operation in energy-savings modes whenever possible (see above) reduce the wear and tear of building services equipment. This increases their service life.	X	(X)	(X)	(X)	(X)	(X)

Table 2 Possible applications of augmented presence detection in buildings. The necessary presence information is marked by crosses [2].

4. Recommendations for action

From the present work, recommendations for action have been derived for the further development of presence detectors and the use of the augmented presence in buildings. These recommendations are aimed at manufacturers of presence detectors and specialist planners or electrical contractors.

- Sensors for detecting augmented presence must not differ significantly from conventional detectors (e.g. PIR). This applies in particular with regard to price, appearance, interfaces, measuring characteristics, installation, commissioning, maintenance and operation.

- The placement, alignment and adjustment of the sensors must not be demanding. Persons without product-specific training must be able to perform installation and commissioning. Changes in room conditions should not require any reconfiguration.
- To detect augmented presence, the method that captures the least amount of personal information should always be chosen. In the case of optical sensors, only non-personal or anonymous data should be output.
- The detection of augmented presence is not useful in residential buildings. Here, predicting occupancy based on conventional presence data already provides great added value; the additional benefit of augmented presence detection is small. For ventilation systems, however, its use should be considered.
- The efficient use of space is important. This can be ensured by the dynamic allocation of resources and by planning according to real requirements. The necessary bases can be provided by the augmented presence detection.
- Wherever possible, data from augmented presence detectors should be made available to all disciplines (lighting, shading, HVACs) and building technology systems (BACS, security, IoT).

5. Perspectives

Although augmented presence detection has only been used occasionally in buildings so far, a significant increase is to be expected. In particular, this can be used to optimize the profitability of buildings and to create data-driven bases for effective planning. On the other hand, the benefits of augmented presence detection with respect to energy efficiency are rather difficult to quantify and need to be further investigated.

The present work has opened several perspectives. Today, augmented presence is not explicitly taken into account in building standards. However, there are many applications for it. Accordingly, the insights from this work should be incorporated into prevailing standards. Researchers should also develop measuring principles that can be installed, commissioned and operated easily by laypersons in different building services applications. Product manufacturers, for their part, should bring products to the market that are compatible with the requirements of presence detection in buildings. In particular, equivalent replacements for conventional solutions are needed. Finally, the benefits of augmented presence in general, and its influence on energy consumption in particular, must be investigated in practical applications.

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